

Successful Thoracoscopic Evacuation of Giant Traumatic Extrapleural Hematoma: Two Cases Report

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Clinical Image

Traumatic extrapleural hematoma is a rare clinical condition defined as hemorrhage between the parietal pleura and endothoracic fascia; is created when the blood cannot escape into the pleural cavity because the parietal pleura is still intact and is usually treated conservatively until spontaneous resolution. However, due to the expansion of hematoma and/or the active bleeding with progression of anemia, surgical treatment might be necessary to control bleeding and lung compression respiratory disorders.

We reported two rare cases of giant traumatic extrapleural hematoma. Etiologic factors were domestic accident in one case and fall from height in the other. We performed thoracoscopic evacuation of a huge extrapleural hematoma, respectively due to severe anemization with shortness of breath and chest pain in a patient and to progressive expansion of hematoma in the other patient.

Careful observation is necessary in this disease. Video-Assisted Thoracic Surgery (VATS) is particularly effective and minimally invasive (**Case 1 and 2 Figures**).

Case 1 - Figure 1: Chest Computed Tomography (CT) scan showing hemothorax (white arrow), a convex extrapleural Hematoma with extrapleural fat sign (yellow arrow), atelectasis of the left lower lobe (dashed arrow) and 7th rib fracture (sky blue arrow).

Case 1 - Figure 2: Operation findings showed an extrapleural hematoma.

Case 2 - Figure 1: Chest Computed Tomography (CT) scan showed a huge lens-like encapsulated extrapleural hematoma.

Case 2 - Figure 2: During exploration, a huge hematoma was detected in the extrapleural space.

Case 2 - Figure 3: Partial pleurectomy to resect a large amount of hematoma was performed by means of VATS.

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